

VIRTUAL PROTOTYPING FOR MEMBRANE APPLICATION IN MICROPLASTIC FILTERING

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ABSTRACT

A virtual prototype was developed using Design thinking (DT), prototyping and Product Lifecycle Management (PLM) to study the feasibility of creating a sustainable microplastic filter made from a polymeric membrane based on polystyrene/poly(ether-ether-ketone) with clay as a filter element. The general objective of the article arises with the aim of devising a product for the future application of a filter attached to washing machines to retain microplastics that come off clothes during the washing stage. Thus, the research was based mainly on studies of scientific articles, magazines and reliable electronic media, and a literature review was also carried out. Therefore, it presents, Identification, selection of works, periods, authors and search strategies, sources, period, keywords and, finally, analysis of the literature collected. For analyzing the results despite the different approaches, the development of applicable, simple and fast particle detection methods continues to be a challenge. Although people's attention is now focused on M/NPs, the focus is still on the detection and danger of M/NPs, and the way to remove M/NPs is relatively less popular. Therefore, it is concluded that from virtual prototyping it was possible to develop a product prototype for better practical knowledge of the applied results of design thinking and to be able to map the creation process of the future product up to the phase of proper disposal at stations collection.

Keywords: Prototyping, Polymeric Membrane, Microplastics.

1. INTRODUCTION

A virtual prototype was developed using Design thinking (DT), prototyping and Product Lifecycle Management (PLM) to study the feasibility of creating a sustainable microplastic filter made from a polystyrene/poly(ether-ether-ketone)-based polymeric membrane with clay as a filter element. The prototype met all proposed sustainability requirements in manufacturing and recycling, adaptability to consumer needs and economic viability. Design Thinking helps to develop the incompetences that designers acquired over several decades in the search to establish a correspondence between human needs and available technical resources, taking into account the practical limitations of the company (Luiz et al., 2023).

In recent decades, the demand for new sustainable and at the same time economically viable products has raised industry interest in the development of such products (Cai et al., 2023). The study of new engineering materials based on mixtures between two or more polymers is an economically viable direction, the insertion of small inorganic particles distributed nanometrically in dispersed phases causes significant improvements in the barrier properties, thermal and mechanical resistance of the polymer (SANTOS, 2011).

Pollution caused by plastic has been a problem for decades, largely due to a consumerist society and incorrect disposal of waste. Despite the reduction in the fragmentation of plastic waste, the material still continues to interact with elements of the environment, which makes the impacts greater. Microplastics are fragments smaller than 5 mm in diameter and very harmful due to their size, they are the most numerically abundant plastic debris in the ocean (CÓZAR et al., 2014; JAMBECK et al., 2015a; LAW; THOMPSON, 2014; SEBILLE et al, 2015). Some of the consequences of plastic pollution are: decreased aesthetic value of the aquatic environment, loss of biodiversity and threat to public health. Environments with fresh water can accumulate numerous plastic particles and fibers, serving as a source, transfer medium and sink for sea water. Other characteristics related to plastics and microplastics is the abundance of these substances close to areas with high populations (LI et al, 2018).

Is Design thinking directly linked to the development of a sustainable filter to solve the problem that generates microplastics during rinsing when washing clothes?

According to Liu et al., 2022 the state of the art directed articles towards solutions for plastic products when they are erased after use and suffer wear due to external influences and decompose into micro and nano sized plastics, i.e. microplastics and nanoplastics , recently, articles sought to develop mitigating solutions. In modern society, microplastics (MP) are found not only in the environment, but also in drinking water, food and consumer products. These

MPs are toxic, carcinogenic, endocrine disruptors and represent a genetic risk, causing many diseases. Despite diverse approaches, the development of applicable, simple and rapid in situ particle detection methods remains a challenge (Kim et al., 2023).

Despite literary gaps, to date, no scientific work has been found on the filter, which consists of a recyclable polymeric material and a mini-pump. Virtual prototyping was used to develop the product and test its viability before moving to physical prototyping. To fill this research gap, the entire process, including DT, prototyping and life cycle management, led to the implementation of the desired product. Virtual prototyping proved to be satisfactory due to financial limitations for physical testing. In the literature, Designing Thinking is found as a popular approach in the practice of business innovation (Cai et al., 2023).

The addition of hydrophilic montmorillonite (MMTH+) to polymer matrices not only promotes a lower glass transition temperature and lower crystallinity of the polymers, but also increases proton conductivity. There is evidence that the incorporation of inorganic oxides into sulfonated poly(ether-ether-ketone) (sPEEK) membranes significantly increases the retention of water bodies therein (Rosas et al., 2014). Therefore, it is essential to achieve the chemical composition and essential properties of composites for the production of materials suitable for reducing environmental effects, using low-cost and high-performance raw materials, in order to produce new hybrid membranes. synthesized for use in CaC or filtration processes.

The general objective of the article arises with the aim of devising a product for the future application of a filter attached to washing machines to retain microplastics that come off clothes during the washing stage. Specifically, Develop a virtual prototype is a mockup, model or digital simulation, with creation and testing being virtual prototyping; optimize, time, cost and quality and requires a pragmatic practice of prototyping using operational means in developing a sustainable product.

DT is directly linked to problem solving, starting with the customer's needs and the ability to overcome them, in addition to meeting their expectations. It is a set of different skills that guarantees the creation or innovation of something exactly the way the client wants it (Liedtka, 2015). For Gould, 2018, DT is not a linear process (convergent thinking) that follows "step-by-step" procedures, but a process that aims to discover connections (divergent thinking) to find new patterns and possible relationships that exist, e.g. in school, even though both types of thinking are necessary within all types of organizations.

It is an approach based on acceptance, collaboration and experimentation, being fundamental elements for the organizational environment to seek closer ties with the market, reducing the chance of losing new offers and opening up opportunities for the business. And it

is worth highlighting that it is a proposal that connects many areas of knowledge in training within a project team, promoting the creation of new ideas and the resolution of obscure problems. In this way, it encourages the creation of prototypes, helping to train people to think openly, reducing the risk of failure and encouraging the participation of individuals in the process in an innovative way with a focus on the user, where learning, idea creation, prototyping, participation and analysis stand out. competition, which result in business strategy and market innovation.

Prototyping is the updating and incorporation of a concept with the intention of communicating or analyzing, with each instance of a design being a prototype before the final product (Kent et. al, 2021). Effective prototyping, early and frequent, has a significant positive impact on the success of a design project (Camburn et al., 2017) and on designers (Gerber, 2009). However, designing optimally and within the limits of time, cost and quality requires a pragmatic practice of prototyping using appropriate means and fidelity (Ulrich & Eppinger, 2016).

Design processes include a range of prototypes that span physical and virtual domains, with each domain having different strengths and weaknesses (Liker & Pereira, 2018). Therefore, there is often a need to transition between domains. This transition often presents challenges, such as having the associated skills and resource requirements for complex multi-domain prototyping, transition cost (time and money), and difficulty in determining the most appropriate domain for resolving product definition issues (Ulrich & Eppinger, 2016).

Prototyping objectives, processes and strategies were explored by design researchers with the purpose of understanding and guiding best practices. Prototypes are built to fulfill a specific purpose (Camere & Bordegoni, 2016), and systematic and purposeful prototyping has been shown to provide significant value for task clarification (Jensen et al., 2017; Auflem, Erichsen, & Steinert, 2019) and later project stages (Camburn et al., 2013; Lauff, Menold, & Wood, 2019; Menold, Jablokow, & Simpson, 2017).

Physical prototypes are used throughout the design process, from the first abstract concepts to the last complete system testing. They bring tangibility to an idea, facilitating a range of purposes (Camburn et al., 2017; Lauff et al., 2018; Mathias, Hicks, Snider, & Ranscombe, 2018). A physical prototype is an unambiguous representation of a concept and is used for various purposes such as form exploration and communication, physical performance and behavior testing, and virtual model analysis validation. Physical prototypes are manufactured at a variety of fidelities and from a variety of materials depending on specific

requirements, from low-fidelity foam and cardboard models (typically employed in early design stages) to sophisticated, high-precision final systems (normally close to final production).

Due to their unambiguous form, physical prototypes offer benefits through tangibility, providing insights into how the user will perceive and interact with the prototype, as well as validation of function or performance (Liker & Pereira, 2018). Haptic interaction with a prototype cannot be replicated in the virtual domain and often results in the use of physical prototypes to validate learning from the virtual prototype. The manufacture of the physical prototype can also expose flaws in the design, its interfaces or in the manufacturing or assembly process. Disadvantages of physical prototyping include manufacturing time and cost, which often increase with fidelity and material requirements (Camburn et al., 2015), expense and complexity associated with effective testing, lack of flexibility once produced, and associated skill to design and manufacturing at different prototype fidelities. Furthermore, physical prototypes often suffer from a lack of version control to document iterations (Erichsen, Sjöman, Steinert, & Welo, 2020), few options for remote collaboration or ways of working, as well as difficulties in extracting and documenting learnings from the prototype.

A virtual prototype is a digital mockup, model or simulation, with the creation and testing of the virtual prototype being virtual prototyping (Wang, 2002). By modeling physical phenomena as a digital process, complex and time-consuming calculations are transferred to a computer and computed quickly, reliably and repeatably. These digital processes enable many advantages for creating virtual models, such as manufacturing planning, simulation and analysis, and visualization of shape permutations without costly physical remanufacturing (Aromaa, 2017; Bharath & Rajashekar, 2015).

Virtual prototyping comprises many tools and processes, ranging from Computer Aided Design (CAD) modeling (e.g. parametric modeling, free-form surface modeling, point clouds, generative design) to systems modeling (e.g. e.g., Agent-Based Modeling) or complex simulation and analysis (e.g., Finite Element Analysis (FEA), Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD)).

Virtual files can be incompatible or interoperable, which means that a virtual prototype often requires multiple representations. Working in the virtual domain offers substantial flexibility, quickly manipulating shape and other parameters, allowing designers to quickly investigate, communicate, or learn about the solution space (Lawson, Herriotts, Malcolm, Gabrecht, & Hermawati, 2015). Virtual prototyping tools provide responsive reconfigurability and can save each state change, allowing version control and a design file to be captured and shared instantly via the internet (Erichsen et al., 2020).

While there are significant benefits to virtual prototyping, several challenges are associated with purely digital design activities. A virtual prototype is intangible, and physical properties such as scale and appearance are difficult to emulate and are often viewed through a two-dimensional screen. Furthermore, there is a learning curve associated with each software, each with different interfaces and restrictions, increasing the complexity and time to create the prototype (Leino, Koivisto, & Riitahuhta, 2013). Good “data hygiene” and rigor in documentation should be considered as soon as a project has a digital element, the management of which can distract designers from the creative process. Furthermore, the virtual prototype will depend on many assumptions and confidence in the model must always be taken into consideration (Berg & Vance, 2017).

PLM (Product Lifecycle Management) is defined as an integrated, information-driven approach to aspects of a product's life, from its design and manufacturing, through its implementation and maintenance, to product removal and final disposal. Another definition of PLM is the integration of business systems that manage the life cycle of a given product. (Stackpole, 2003). PLM can be segmented into five phases (Dias, 2009), extraction and manufacturing

– phase that integrates the extraction and preparation stage of the raw materials used and the manufacture of products or intermediate products of the process; product manufacturing – phase that integrates the manufacturing procedures for parts of a given product and covers the suppliers that contribute to its manufacturing; use of the product by the customer – this phase includes energy consumption for using the product, maintenance, repair and the use of goods or services necessary for the correct functioning of the product; end of useful life – phase that consists of the means of eliminating the product, which can be: recycling, reuse, incineration, disposal in landfills, among others and transportation – this phase is present from the beginning of the product's life cycle and ranges from the process of transporting raw materials, shipping the product to customers, and collecting the product at the end of its useful life.

The article is basically structured in five stages: the first stage the introduction, where the problem and objectives can be identified, the second stage the methodology where methods are presented, the third stage the results, the fourth the discussion and final considerations will be carried out in the last stage, where it is verified whether the article achieved its objectives and whether it answered the research questions.

2 METHODS

Thus, the research was based mainly on studies of scientific articles, magazines and reliable electronic media, and a literature review was also carried out. Therefore, it presents, Identification, selection of works, periods, authors and search strategies, sources, period, keywords and, finally, analysis of the literature collected. The analysis method will be the qualitative approach. This type of research, according to Cooper and Schindler (2011), includes a set of interpretative techniques that seek to describe, decode, translate and give meaning to the phenomenon studied. Objectively, the research is qualitative and considered applied, whose main objective is the generation of knowledge, aimed at solving specific problems. Therefore, it presents the exploratory and bibliographic analysis. After consulting the articles, an evaluation was carried out based on summaries and keywords to refine the research results, which consists of the filter available on the journal portal that performs the ranking based on the score of the documents retrieved in each search. for a total of refined articles. Thus, it proposes the preparation of a polymeric mixture of the polymers sPEEK (sulfonated Poly-ether-ether-ketone), sPS (sulfonated Polystyrene) and MB 22298-CN (Interfacial Agent) in the solvent DMF (Dimethylformamide).

Through Designing thinking Seeking to develop a product that was effective and, at the same time, sustainable, creating a filter with the aim of retaining microplastics that come off clothes when washed, having been developed to be adaptable to the water outlet of the Washing machine. Called FILTIMP, still in its early stages, the concept is similar to others designed mainly to filter microplastics, but using fully recyclable materials, with concern for the environment and the future of society.

After completing the three stages (DT, prototyping and PLM) it is possible to advance to the DT implementation stage, since the virtual prototype showed that it is possible to purchase and adapt existing commercial parts to manufacture the product.

1) Analysis and objectivity stage: After the immersion, it was understood the need to create a solution that could minimize the emission of microplastics from domestic consumption into domestic sewage.

2) Ideation stage: This was the stage of generating ideas aligned with the challenges, to create a filter capable of retaining microplastics. After brainstorming, it was decided to prototype the filter inspired by a filter and minipump already on the market.

- 3) Prototype stage: After going through all these phases, the group officially selected the most productive ideas in solving the problem, that is, it developed an incremental innovation that was beneficial to users and in a resolute way.
- 4) Implementation stage: Phase yet to be carried out as it is necessary to first encapsulate the polymeric mixtures to carry out the experiments.

Figure 1 – Legend

Source: Authors, 2023

3 RESULTS

According to Kim et al., 2023 despite the diverse approaches, the development of applicable, simple and fast in situ particle detection methods continues to be a challenge. Although people's attention is now focused on M/NPs, the focus is still on the detection and danger of M/NPs, and the way to remove M/NPs is relatively less popular. Comparing the advantages and disadvantages of different methods will help more researchers choose the appropriate method for their research (Liu et al., 2022).

According to Braun et al., (2021) the emergence of microplastics (MP) in foods, such as drinks in plastic bottles. It's a huge concern for the public. Existing analysis methods focus on determining the number of particles and require complex sampling instruments, laboratory infrastructure and image recognition methods, which are often time-consuming. A complete routine analysis of fine particles in food is not yet possible. According to Ngo et al., (2019)

microplastic (MP) pollution in the aquatic environment has recently been documented as an emerging environmental threat due to its negative impact on the ecosystem. There are many fountains, but they are all made from synthetic materials. Sources of PM are cosmetic and personal care products, putrefaction or abrasion processes of other plastic products, textiles and tires, bitumen and paints for road markings. Due to their low density and small subatomic particle size they can be easily disposed of in sewers. Consequently, municipal wastewater treatment plants (WTP) have been identified as important receptors of PM before being released into natural water sources.

Oßmann et al., (2017) when analyzing microplastics in food, for toxicological reasons, it is important to obtain clear identification of particles up to a size of at least 1 µm. A reliable optical analysis technique that makes this possible is micro-Raman spectroscopy. After particles have been isolated by filtration, analysis is typically performed directly on the filter surface. To obtain high-quality Raman spectra, the membrane filter material should not cause interference with the background and Raman signal during spectrum acquisition. To facilitate the use of automatic particle detection membrane filters must also have special ocular properties.

3.1 Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) Analysis

The Fourier Transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) technique is based on the vibrations of atoms in a molecule when electromagnetic radiation in the infrared range (4000 – 400 cm⁻¹) is incident on it (CONSTANTINO, 2006). The radiation absorbed by a molecule is converted into vibration energy, this energy is recorded by a spectrometer in the form of absorption bands and used to provide evidence of the presence of functional groups in the organic structure. Chemical modifications in composites can be verified from analysis of FTIR spectra. In Figure 2, the FT-IR spectra (4000-400 cm⁻¹) of the analyzed composites can be seen.

Figure 2 – FTIR spectra of the composites sPS/sPEEK 0% clay, sPS/sPEEK 1% clay, sPS/sPEEK 3% clay and sPS/sPEEK 5% clay

Source: ANA, 2020

3.2 Scanning Electron Microscopy Analysis

For better visualization, the ideal would be to focus on the “interface” of this lighter structure with the darker matrix to see if there is a good integration of the phases or if it is possible to perceive a separation between them. Figure 3 illustrates a very interesting image. It is possible to observe a uniformity in the circular sizes of the structures and a tendency to coalescence between the structures, showing the integration of the phases. These three brighter structures below are probably modified MMT clay. This micrograph suggests that there was a good interaction between the polymers making up the mixture, as well as the modified mineral clay.

Figure 3 – Scanning Electron Microscopy

Source: ANA, 2020

4 DISCUSSION

Immersion or empathy stage: The scenario observed by the group was that with the growth of plastic production after the Second World War, billions of tons of waste accumulated in the environment. Microplastics can be found everywhere today, for example in Arctic snow, table salt, tap water and synthetic clothing.

The prototype met all proposed sustainability requirements. Inspired by creating a prototype based on existing knowledge of commercial parts, it was thought to couple two pieces of equipment already on the market: A quick-connect line filter, commonly used for filtering beer craft between the barrel and the tap (or between the fermenter and the barrel) and a 12v mini water pump. With the help of artificial intelligence, an image was generated that shows the idealized coupling, resulting in the desired prototype for carrying out the tests. The filter, named FILTImp, is made up of two main parts: a filter, made with recyclable polymeric material containing the polymeric capsule, and an attached mini-pump which, when activated by the washing machine, pumps the dirty water into the sewer at the same time. which filters dirt particles and microplastics. It was designed to be used by vulnerable communities and can be attached to a tap or hose and adapted to a washing machine. The group has not yet built a working prototype, but predicts that the capsule will have to be changed every two months. At the end of its life cycle, the filter element cannot be disposed of in household waste due to the microplastics incorporated in its membrane. In this way, the students devised the creation of delivery locations where they could be collected and transformed into a new type of plastic material, while the capsule could be reused in a new filter.

The theoretical gap in which the study is directly linked to problem solving, starting with the customer's needs and the ability to overcome them, in addition to meeting their expectations. Academic relevance is to design in an optimized way and within the limits of time, cost and quality, requiring a pragmatic practice of prototyping using operational means and fidelity (Ulrich & Eppinger, 2016). Design processes include a range of prototypes that span physical and virtual domains, with each domain having different strengths and weaknesses (Liker & Pereira, 2018). Prototyping processes and strategies have been explored by design researchers for the purpose of understanding and guiding best practices, and this transition often presents challenges such as having the associated skills and resource requirements for complex, cross-domain prototyping, transition cost, and difficulty in determining the most protected domain to resolve product definition issues (Ulrich & Eppinger, 2016).

5 CONSIDERATIONS

Using virtual prototyping, it was possible to develop a product prototype for better practical knowledge of the applied results of design thinking and to be able to map the creation process of the future product up to the phase of proper disposal at collection points. Due to financial limitations to enable physical tests, virtual prototyping proved to be satisfactory in meeting the requirements for consolidating knowledge about Project and Product Engineering. Physical prototypes have advantages such as testing physical performance and validating virtual models, but they also have disadvantages such as cost and lack of version control. Virtual prototypes, on the other hand, are digital simulations that can be used for testing and development. A specific case study involves the development of a sustainable filter to trap microplastics from laundry water.

The objectives used to solve this research problem arise with the aim of devising a product for the future application of a filter attached to washing machines to retain microplastics. Design Thinking is directly linked to problem solving and meeting customer expectations. Prototyping is an essential part of the design process, involving physical and virtual prototypes. Physical prototypes have advantages such as testing physical performance and validating virtual models, but they also have disadvantages such as cost and lack of version control. Work from this research will make it possible to confirm the methodology used to manufacture polymer composites based on sulfonated polystyrene (sPS) and sulfonated poly(ether-ether-ketone) (sPEEK), in the preparation of polymeric filter mixtures and MB 22298-CN (Interfacial Agent) in the solvent DMF (Dimethylformamide).

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7 DECLARATION OF CONFLICT OF INTEREST

There is no conflict of interest

8 FINANCING STATEMENT

There is not

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